

TECHNOLOGY OF DEVELOPMENT OF LEADERSHIP ACTIVITY IN TEENAGERS BASED ON COMPETENCE APPROACH

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Annotation: The article characterizes leadership competencies, defines the features of their formation, and identifies factors contributing to their formation.

Keywords: leadership, teenagers, factors, formation, development.

INTRODUCTION

In the modern world, a fairly large number of teenagers are distinguished by the presence of leadership competencies. These teenagers will become the adults of tomorrow who successfully found start-up companies, rise from entry-level positions to senior management, lead societies toward political change, oversee scientific breakthroughs, and inspire and transform the world around them.

Leadership competence is understood as those knowledge, abilities and skills that allow a leader to manage other people, implement changes and inspire like-minded people [2].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Indeed, close observation of any schoolyard, high school classroom, or other place where teenagers gather makes it easy to identify leadership patterns characteristic of modern teenagers. Some teenagers show a natural tendency to influence the attitudes, goals and behavior of their peers, while others more easily adapt to the role of followers.

For some, these roles will remain quite consistent, while others may flexibly switch between leader and follower in different situations and contexts. This relative flexibility suggests that leadership can be meaningfully influenced and intervened during adolescence.

Unfortunately, there is a critical knowledge gap that hinders our ability to take advantage of this flexibility and encourage and develop future leaders. Even though leadership begins to develop at an early age, theoretical developments and related empirical research have focused almost exclusively on adults.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During adolescence, teen leaders already have a significant impact on the world around them. It is important to note that these leaders demonstrate future potential, not just current success; They are not like the average politician or company

president and do not occupy the same positions as them. This highlights the need for an empirical understanding of adolescent leadership itself and highlights ways in which the adult leaders of tomorrow can be better understood and developed to maximize their effectiveness in the workplace of the future [1].

Despite this research gap, many stakeholders (e.g., educators, parents, policy makers, employers) are investing heavily in understanding leadership potential and leadership behavior in early childhood, when multiple pathways of leadership development develop into diverse sets of knowledge, skills, skills and other characteristics related to leadership behavior in adulthood.

At the same time, adolescence typically represents a critical entry point into the world of work in most Western industrialized cultures, as well as a time for increased involvement in other leadership skills during adolescence.

Compared with both children and adults, adolescents tend to exhibit increased social sensitivity, a finding that is consistent across neural, hormonal, and behavioral levels of analysis, and adolescents also tend to be more embedded in social hierarchies. Regarding the latter, adolescents demonstrate reasonable consensus in determining the level of social status, competence and reputation of their peers, which means that they are not only developing their own potential leadership skills, but are also likely to be especially sensitive to their development in others. .

Thus, it seems clear that adolescence is a developmental period that provides a critical opportunity for scientific understanding of the early emergence of leadership, its development, and its impact on leadership in adulthood.

One area that practitioners should explore in the context of early leadership is personality and individual differences. Adolescence is a time of remarkable change, with development occurring simultaneously in cognitive, physical, personal and social areas.

These models highlight two main areas of development [2]:

- 1) development of cognitive and behavioral self-regulation skills, including decision making and inhibitory control, and
- 2) increasing sensitivity to reward, including attention to social indicators such as reputation and social status.

Both areas are clearly relevant to leadership, and as traits related to leadership become increasingly differentiated throughout adolescent development, it becomes especially important and useful to be able to measure these traits and examine their predictive value for leadership processes and participate in contextual interventions. The studies reviewed identified a number of individual difference variables relevant to professional leadership success in adulthood, drawn from many areas of research,

including social psychology, industrial-organizational psychology, and management.

Examples include the personality trait of social dominance—a tendency to act assertively combined with a desire to be a leader, often nested within extraversion—which is regularly associated with leadership evaluations and performance.

Self-control is another important dispositional characteristic leading to professional success and leadership, often serving as one of the strongest—if not the strongest—predisposition to professional leadership in a variety of contexts. Although several other individual differences have been associated with leadership in adults, it is striking that the two strongest correlates—social dominance (a facet of extraversion) and self-control—are directly related to two major domains within personality development in adolescence.

CONCLUSION

Thus, adolescence serves as a critical period for the development of social skills and social perception, both key processes underlying leadership. Leaders' knowledge of their group members plays a critical role in their ability to manage the group, assign specific members tasks, and allocate resources in a manner that promotes both the group's development and the achievement of its goals.

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